

CENTRAL FERGANA (YOZYAVON) WATER WAREHOUSE AND HIS IMPACT IN THE ZONE CHANGES

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Abstract. *In the article Central Fergana (Yozyavon) water warehouse effect landscape-ecological zone of changes common description given Environment changes surface brought factors shown . Soil occurred in the section morphological changes illuminated.*

Keywords: *water storage, landscape, ecology, hydrogen, anthropogenic, impact zone, soil section, soil morphology.*

Introduction. The President of Republic of Uzbekistan on June 17 , 2019 PF No. 5742 " Village in the farm land and water resources efficient use measures on " dated July 10 , 2020 PF No. 6024 until 2030 has been period Uzbekistan Republic of water farm development concept confirmation about ” decrees in the country water with depends all areas water with stable and guaranteed provide for irrigation systems development and water resources efficient and reasonable use according to wide scope things done increase necessity shown .

It's hot and dry climate conditions irrigated farming to be done of regions almost in all water distribution improve issue the most important from problems is considered Rivers water spending year during from season to season and from that year this per year changed stands Our country in the conditions of the village in the farm to water has been demand increased in the seasons the majority the river and in streams water sharp decreases, some in scores completely dry remains. Such in the circumstances the river and streams from the water full and efficient use their flow procedure manage necessity appear will be Year during the river of streams changed standing and his area across uneven distributed Water warehouse set up to do necessity gives birth Water warehouse flow seasons and years according to in order puts, channel and another water transfer facilities with together regions across again to distribution opportunity creates

Waterable of lands water supply improve and new lands appropriation in order to Ferghana of the valley four side are available have been many mountain of rivers medium and high in streams water warehouses built. Irrigation systems combined folk channels conducted. This stabilized the structure of water supplying from more watery rivers to less watery rivers.

South Ferghana mountain rivers of cone spreads northern lower in parts, Central of Ferghana a lot in places water lack of serious problem Irrigation networks developed to be absorbed though of fields some parts water from scarcity degraded village economy from circulation out gone At the same time water warehouses effect zone lower in parts of soils swamping and salinity like processes observed.

The Central Fergana water warehouse which is located in Central Asia has influence in the zone different sectors, including rural economy, industry and household needs provide for important water source is considered However, such water warehouses Create and of them use inevitable respectively complicated ecological to changes take comes, in particular, their effect zones soil features. The Central Ferghana water warehouse existence as a result surface came soil changes dynamics to understand from the ground efficient use and in the region stable

development for is necessary. This in the introduction water warehouse effect in the zone soil to the dynamics effect doer factors , including hydrological changes , village economy practice and ecological effects about common information given This factors lighting through this research water economy infrastructure and soil properties between mutually dependence each bilaterally to understand contribution to add and that's it through The Central Ferghana water warehouse consists of nearby land resources stable use according to justified decisions acceptance to do from facilitation

Research methodology. Studies were held in The Central Ferghana water warehouse surroundings to the environment effect reach on the borders. Water warehouse effect in the zone landscapes and their components and happened to them changes were studied. In field studies observation, historical geographical comparison, morphometric, morphogenetic of methods was used. Analytical studies in laboratory conditions soil science in practice wide standard methods used based on done increased

To the topic about of literature analysis. Water warehouses in effect environmental landscape environment and ameliorative status to study K.N. Dyakonov, A.M. Nikitin, M.I. Lvovich, G.V. Voropaev, A.B. Avakyan , S.G. Altunun , E.G. Kaguchin , V. Nazarov, V. Schultz, S. Sobolev, K. Sitnik, A. Alibekov , F. Khikmatov , A. Rakhmatullaev, V. Rafikov , K. Sharofuddinova , Yu. Sultanov , Sh. Azimov, I. Abdulkasimova , R. Pirnazarov , I.Kh. Abdullaev, I.E. Like Karimov many scientists works dedicated. This of work most of them abroad, in particular in Russia done increased. In our republic, including Ferghana in the valley water warehouses surroundings to the environment to the effect about studies are a lot.

Research of the territory soils Ferghana province soil research reach during A.N. Rozanov, A.M. Pankov, N.V. Kimber, M.U. Umarov, V. Yu. Isakov, G'. Yuldashev, M. Isagaliev , A. Turdaliev and another many scientists learned But water warehouses effect point of view in terms of separately studies not held .

Analysis and results. Water storage - dams using the water collection and distribution for applied artificial water basin. Dams to the task according to two type divides [3, 7]:

- a) water level to raise intended dams. They are energy, water transport, river or from the channel water get purposes will be built;
- b) water collect and the river flow manage in order to build dams.

Waterable farming conditions complex - complex goals looking forward to will be built. Collective to use intended reservoirs people in the farm one how much networks (irrigation, water supply, electricity energy, shipping, fishing, floods against to fight and others) satisfies.

Water warehouses show effect in the zone water food improve with together to the environment serious effects.

This effect the results are "... natural landscapes changes, their new types, human hydrotechnical facilities (canal, dam, dam, etc.) others), water press with depends hydrogen landscapes, saline, marshy fields, natural of landscapes natural - anthropogenic types with is manifested in " exchange ". will be [6]. So, the landscape of the area is ecological status natural-geographic, hydrogen and man-made factors forms.

The Central Fergana (Yozyavon) water warehouse Ferghana province Writer of the district Yangiabad MFY at set up hydrotechnical facility being

Table 1

T/r	Water warehouse about data	Parameters	Measurement unit
General information			
1	Name	Central Ferghana Reservoir	
2	Province	Ferghana	
3	Fog	Writer	
4	Address	Yangiabad MFY	
5	Geometric coordinates X	40.6404679	
6	Geometric Y coordinates	71.5153464	
7	Class	1	
8	Water warehouse of the dam type	Do not lift from the sand	
9	Exploitation year	2013 year	
9	Organization name	Fergana Region Water Reservoir Utilization Department	
10	Status	Under construction	
of the dam geometric dimensions			
11	Dam height (-h)	20	m
12	Dam width (- b [m])	250-270	m
13	of the dam length (- l [m])	25.5	km
14	Dam high part of width (- b top [m])	9	m
15	Dam of the nucleus height (- h core [m])	30	m
16	Dam of the nucleus width (-b kernel [m])	0.60	m
17	Dam of the nucleus high some width (- b) Core-top ([m])	2.60	m
18	High otkos slope	1.68	
19	Bottom otkos slope	1.4	
of the dam each one part (dam , core , screen) physical-mechanical characteristics			
20	of the dam density (- r [kg/m ³])	1.6	
21	Elasticity modulus (- E [kN /m ²])		
22	Poisson coefficient (- n [-])		
23	Friction angle (- φ [°])	24 ⁰	
24	Stseplenie (- c [kN /m ²])		
25	Core density (- [kg/m ³])	1.7	
26	Core modulus of elasticity Eyadro ([kN /m ²])		
27	Core Poisson coefficient (- n) kernel		
28	Core friction angle (- φ [°])	35 ⁰	
29	Core stseplenie (- c [kN /m ²])		

From reservoirs of Fergana region head of the utilization department S. Khasanov

Conclusions and suggestions . Under the influence of the Central Fergana (Yozyavon) reservoir, natural-anthropogenic landscapes were formed instead of natural landscapes. New lands were developed, water supply of existing irrigated lands improved. New landscapes of orchards and vineyards were created.

The increase in water supply in the region has also brought about some negative changes. Adir and hill took slope plains in the zone irrigation erosion increased. Lower in the zone while sir of the waters level rose, their mineralization level increased. Partially swamping and salinity processes developed of the area ecological ameliorative situation moderate without storage for of irrigation thrifty technologies, in particular drop by drop and underground watering current to do it is necessary Plowman and to the soil processing horizontals in the direction of organize to do erosion prevention takes Sizot of the waters level from the critical depth not pass necessary for monitoring work preventive measures when possible strengthen to the goal according to will be

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